

Teachers' Assessment Literacy and Assimilation Skills of the Junior High School Students

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Abstract. The study aimed to look into the influence of teachers' assessment literacy towards assimilation skills of the junior high school students. In this study, the researcher selected the 210 junior high school students in selected secondary public schools in New Corella, Davao del Norte as the respondents of the study. Stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the respondents. Non-experimental quantitative research design using descriptive-correlational method was employed. The data collected were subjected on the following statistical tools: Mean, Pearson Moment Product Correlation and Regression Analysis. Findings revealed that teachers' assessment literacy and assimilation skills of the junior high school students in selected secondary public schools in New Corella, Davao del Norte were rated as moderately extensive. Further, correlation analysis demonstrated that there is a significant relationship between teachers' assessment literacy and assimilation skills of the junior high school students in selected secondary public schools in New Corella, Davao del Norte. Evidently, regression analysis proved that teachers' assessment literacy in terms of fairness and equity; students' involvement; and feedback and communication significantly influence the assimilation skills of junior high school students among public secondary schools in New Corella in Davao Del Norte.

KEY WORDS

1. Educational management 2. teachers' assessment literacy 3. assimilation skills of the junior high school students

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1. Introduction

Teachers' assessment literacy is a critical component of 21st-century learning because it enables educators to design assessments that measure the skills, competencies, and qualities needed for success in the modern world. These assessments support the development of well-rounded, adaptable learners who can thrive in a rapidly evolving global landscape. 21st-century learning recognizes that students have diverse learning styles and strengths. Teachers with assessment literacy can design multimodal assessments that allow students to demonstrate their understanding in various ways, whether through written work, oral presentations, multimedia projects, or collaborative activities. Thus, teachers can design assessments that evaluate students' ability to work in diverse, multicultural contexts, aligning with the global nature of 21st-century challenges and opportunities. Firoozi et al. (2019) affirmed that teachers who are assessment literate can design assessments that align with their instructional goals, ensuring

that assessments accurately measure what students are expected to learn. This leads to more effective teaching strategies and helps students achieve better learning outcomes. Adding more, Mussawy (2014) noted that teachers with assessment literacy can analyze assessment results to identify students' strengths and weaknesses. Likewise, Hameed-Ur-Rehman and Baig (2017) noted that when teachers can accurately interpret assessment data, they can identify struggling students and provide targeted interventions. This might involve offering additional support, adjusting teaching strategies, or providing differentiated instruction to address specific learning gaps. Meanwhile, Askin and Demirel (2018) described assimilation skills as the ability of students to understand, process, and make sense of the information they encounter in various forms, such as texts, lectures, visuals, and multimedia. These skills involve extracting meaning, identifying key concepts, recognizing relationships between ideas, and drawing conclusions from the information presented. According to Catts and Kamhi (2017) assimilation skills enable students to break down complex problems and analyze them systematically. They can identify relevant information, assess different perspectives, and formulate well-reasoned solutions. Also, Buslon and Alieto (2019) noted that strong assimilation skills contribute to better academic performance. Students who can understand and synthesize information are more likely to excel in exams, assignments, and projects. However, reports indicated that poor assimilation skills remains an increasing problem among school administrators worldwide. For instance, Suminar (2017) reported that poor assimilation skills often lead to difficulties in understanding and grasping new concepts, which can result in lower grades and academic performance. Students struggle to keep up with the curriculum and may need additional support to bridge gaps in their understanding. Moreover, Lopes and Cunha (2017)

noted that students have trouble comprehending information, they miss out on the opportunity to engage deeply with the subject matter, which can hinder their ability to build a solid foundation of knowledge. Taking things in Philippine setting, Conoza (2022) reported that weak assimilation skills have a lasting impact on students' educational and professional paths. They face challenges in higher education and in careers that require strong communication, critical thinking, and problem-solving abilities. Accordingly, students who struggle in this area may be less likely to engage in continuous self-education and professional development throughout their lives. Adding more, Tomas et al. (2021) found that poor assimilation skills lead to fragmented knowledge and gaps in understanding. Over time, this affect students' ability to connect different concepts and topics, hindering their holistic understanding of the world. While assessment literacy and students' assimilation skills have been studied independently, there is a scarcity of research that explicitly considers the altruistic teaching approach as a mediator between these two variables. Existing research tends to focus more on the direct relationship between assessment practices and student outcomes. Thus, it is on this context that the researcher felt the need to fill in the research gap of conducting a study in the Philippine setting, particularly in New Corella, Davao del Norte using a quantitative approach. Specifically, the researcher made used regression analysis to determine which among the domains of teachers' assessment literacy significantly influence the assimilation skills of the junior high school students, which is found to be scarce.

1.1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework of the Study—The study is anchored on the Social Cognitive Theory by Bandura (1986). Accordingly, the quality of interactions between teachers and students, influenced by the teachers' teaching approach and their ability to fos-

Fig. 1. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework

ter a caring and supportive atmosphere. The classroom setting created by teachers, characterized by their teaching methods, communication style, and classroom management practices. Hence, the Social Cognitive Theory provides a framework to understand how personal, environmental, and behavioral factors interact to shape the relationship between the assessment literacy, and assimilation skills of students. This theoretical lens emphasizes the importance of fair assessment practices and the influence of both teachers and their instructional practices on student outcomes. In support, Wang et al. (2022) proposed that assessment-literate teachers cre-

ate assessments that align with learning objectives and curriculum standards. This ensures that the assessments accurately measure what students are expected to learn. As a result, teachers can tailor their instruction to address specific areas where students are struggling in terms of assimilation. Adding more, Deluca et al. (2013) intellectualized that assessment-literate teachers can involve students in the assessment process by making them aware of learning goals and criteria for success. This empowers students to take ownership of their learning and set personal goals for improving their information comprehension.

2. Methodology

This section contains the research design, research respondents, research instrument, data gathering procedure, and data analysis.

2.1. *Research Design*—The researcher employed quantitative non-experimental design utilizing correlational technique of research to gather data ideas, facts and information related to the study, the researcher. Quantitative re-

search as described by Bhandari (2020) is a research strategy that focuses on quantifying the collection and analysis of data. Accordingly, quantifying is formed from a deductive approach where emphasis is placed on the test-

ing of theory, shaped by empiricist and positivist philosophies, while, non-experimental research is a research that lacks the manipulation of an independent variable. Rather than manipulating an independent variable, researchers conducting non-experimental research simply measure variables as they naturally occur in real world. Meanwhile, descriptive-correlational research according to Myers and Well (2013) examines how the independent variable influences the dependent variable and establishes cause and effect relationship between variables. In this study the researcher was able to look into the relationship between two variables— teachers' assessment literacy and assimilation skills of junior high school students. In this connection, the study focused on the exploring which domains of teachers' assessment literacy significantly influence the assimilation skills of junior high school students. In this study, the use of descriptive-correlational was appropriate because the researcher only focused on the behavioral aspect of the respondents and the researcher was unable to perform an experiment in controlled set-up.

2.2. Ethical Consideration—The researcher observed promptly the protocols deemed necessary as the standard guidelines in carrying out the research study following the study protocol assessments criteria, particularly in managing the population and data. The survey questionnaires with supporting authors were submitted for further evaluation. After the approval from the Ethics Committee the researcher proceeded to the next phase of the study. Informed Consent. The researcher asked for the permission of respondents through a written informed consent. They were properly informed about the purpose of the study and ample explanations were given to them for better understanding of the reason for their participation so that they can choose whether to participate or not. It was made clear that respondents involvement in the study is volun-

tary. If ever they would refuse to participate, they were not forced by the researcher. Besides, the researcher was cautious to assure the respondents' psychological well-being. A written permission from the respondents were secured from them. The researcher informed the respondents that the study aimed to conduct a study on the factors that hinder/promote the assimilation skills of junior high school students in relation to teachers' assessment literacy, and may contribute to the enhancement. Vulnerability of Research Participants. The respondents of the study are teachers so they are not considered vulnerable since all of them are in legal age, and, they are not considered highly vulnerable in the psychological aspect. The researcher emphasized that the survey was set at the respondents' convenience. Also, the researcher protected the confidentiality of the information disclosed. Privacy and Confidentiality. This study observed the data Privacy Act of 2012 wherein the researcher assured that the data cannot be traced back to the respondents which will be the real source of information, to protect the identities of the participants. Moreover, the researcher assured that no personal data would be shared without the consent of the respondents. Thus, to ensure that no personal data would be exposed, the access was limited to the researcher alone. To protect the privacy of the respondents, it was assured that the researcher is the only person that could access the data on the survey. After the necessary data was collected, the researcher permanently disposed all the survey questionnaires and deleted the data result to assure that data cannot be traced back to the respondents who were the real source of information. Risk, Benefits and Safety - In administering the survey questionnaires, the researcher fully disclosed to the respondents the nature of their participation and explained thoroughly and properly the purpose and benefits of the study as well as the confidentiality of their responses as stated in the online survey ques-

tionnaire. The respondents, without restrictions will be able to ask questions related to the study. Further, the researcher ensured that the respondents were not be subjected to harm in any ways whatsoever. Moreover, the questionnaire and interview guide that were used in this study did not contain any degrading or unacceptable statements offensive to the respondents of the study. Likewise, this study is designed purely to collect academic information related to the study and they were not asked with personal information. To minimize inconvenience, the researcher made sure that the respondents were given ample time to answer the survey questionnaire. The respondents were given freedom not to answer questions which made them feel any psychological and emotional distress and they would be free to withdraw as a respondent of the study if they would feel that they cannot discuss the information that being asked from them. The researcher valued their participation and placed their welfare as the highest priority during the course of the study. Justice. To avoid impartiality in choosing the respondents, the researcher regarded all respondents equal regardless if they would be respondent in the survey. The researcher did not prejudiced in choosing the respondents of the study. Anybody who fitted the qualifications of being bonafied enrolled students in the purposively selected schools. During the conduct of the study, the researcher made certain to respect the respondents by interrupting as little time as possible to the routine of the respondents. To compensate for the time spent during data gathering, the researcher gave tokens of appreciation to the respondents. This token was an assortment of souvenir. The tokens were sent via courier, and these was sealed carefully in a package. Also, each tokens were sanitized before having it sent to your doorstep.

2.3. Research Respondents—The respondents of the study were the junior high school students in in selected secondary public schools

in New Corella, Davao del Norte. The sample size for the selection of the respondents was 210 which was taken from the total numbers of the junior high school students on the selected public secondary schools. Stratified random sampling technique was utilized in the selection of the 300 respondents in this study. According to Pandey (2015) stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. In stratified random sampling, or stratification, the strata are formed based on members' shared attributes or characteristics such as income or educational attainment Stratified random sampling is appropriate in this study because because there is heterogeneity in a population that can be classified with ancillary information. In this study, certain inclusion criteria were implemented in determining the respondents of the study. The primary consideration of this study was to choose respondents who could provide information to achieve the purpose of this study. Hence, only those bonafied enrolled junior high school students in New Corella in Davao del Norte, and who voluntarily signed the ICF and parental consent were given the survey questionnaires. Moreover, the study was delimited only to the nature of the problem based on the research questions and thus it did not consider the socio economic status of the students.

2.4. Research Instrument—The study made use of adapted and modified survey questionnaires to suit the current investigation. The scaling was done by having one-half of the value of 5 as average cut-off point or the fair level, with a uniform interval of 0.80. Also, the survey questionnaires undergone validation by the external and internal panel of experts. The first tool is about teachers' assessment literacy. This was questionnaire was based on the idea of Rahimi et al. (2021) with four indicators namely: fairness and equity; students' involvement; feedback and communication; and technology in assessment. The reliability of the

new scale obtained Cronbach’s alpha value of 0.932 interpreted as excellent, indicating high reliability and consistency among the items. In the manner of answering the questionnaire, the respondents made use the 5-Likert scale. As

a guide in determining the extent of teachers’ assessment literacy, the researcher made use the range of means, description and interpretation as presented below:

Scale Descriptive Ratings and Interpretation on Teachers’ Assessment Literacy

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The teachers’ assessment literacy is always observed.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The teachers’ assessment literacy is oftentimes observed.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The teachers’ assessment literacy is sometimes observed.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The teachers’ assessment literacy is rarely observed.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The teachers’ assessment literacy is never observed.

2.5. *Data Gathering Procedure*—Steps were undergone by the researcher in conducting the study after the validation of the research questionnaire. Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher secured the permission to conduct the study. The researcher secured the endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, and the ethical clearance certificate from Research Ethics Committee (REC). The endorsement letter from the Dean of the Graduate School in Rizal Memorial Colleges, Inc., Davao City, and the ethical clearance certificate from Research Ethics Committee (REC) were attached to the permission letters to be endorsed to the schools division superintendent, and then to the school principals of the selected secondary public schools in New Corella,

Davao del Norte. Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. The researcher proceeded to the distribution of the research instrument to the respondents after the approval to conduct the study. The study was conducted last January 4-5, 2024. Upon the distribution of the questionnaires, the benefits of the survey was briefly discussed and explained to the identified respondents of the study. For the administration of the questionnaire, the respondents of the study were given enough testing time for the questionnaires to be finished. After which, the data collected were subjected to quantitative analysis. Collation and Statistical Treatment of Data. After the data retrieval of the questionnaire, the scores of each respondents was tallied to organized the data per indicator. After which, each score were subjected to descriptive and inferential analysis using SPSS.

Scale Descriptive Ratings and Interpretation on the Assimilation Skills of Junior High School Students

Range of Mean	Descriptive Level	Interpretation
4.20 – 5.00	Very Extensive	The assimilation skills of junior high school students is always manifested.
3.40 – 4.19	Extensive	The assimilation skills of junior high school students is oftentimes manifested.
2.60 – 3.39	Moderately Extensive	The assimilation skills of junior high school students is sometimes manifested.
1.80 – 2.59	Less Extensive	The assimilation skills of junior high school students is seldom manifested.
1.00 – 1.79	Not Extensive	The assimilation skills of junior high school students is never manifested.

2.6. *Data Analysis—*

The following were the statistical tools utilized by the researcher in processing the gathered data:

Mean. This was useful in characterizing the teachers' assessment literacy and assimilation skills of junior high school students in New Corella, Davao del Norte. Mean is descriptive statistics that tend to measure how the score clustered. This was used to supply answers to objectives 1 and 2. Pearson Product Moment Correlation. This was utilized to determine the significance on the relationship between teach-

ers' assessment literacy and assimilation skills of junior high school students in New Corella, Davao del Norte. It is a statistical measure of the strength of a linear relationship between paired data. This was used to supply answers to objective 3. Multiple Linear Regression Analysis. It was applied to evaluate the significance which domains of teachers' assessment literacy significantly influence the assimilation skills of junior high school students in New Corella, Davao del Norte. This was used to supply answers to objective 4.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the results generated from the data gathered. It is sequenced based on the objectives of the study as presented in the first chapter. Thus, it presents the extents of teachers' assessment literacy and assimilation skills of junior high school students in selected secondary public schools in New Corella, Davao del Norte; the significant relationship between teachers' assessment literacy and assimilation skills of junior high school students in selected secondary public schools in New Corella, Davao del Norte; and the influence of teachers' assessment literacy on the assimilation skills of junior high school students in selected secondary public schools in New Corella, Davao del Norte.

3.1. Teachers' Assessment Literacy of Junior High School Student—Fairness and Equity. Specifically, examining the domain of fairness and equity results on Table 1 reveal that its category mean is 3.17 described as moderately extensive which means that this particular domain on teachers' assessment literacy of the junior high school students is sometimes observed. This means that the awareness of potential biases and ensure that their assessments are fair and equitable for all students, regardless of their backgrounds, cultures, or learning styles is sometimes observed among junior high school students in in selected secondary public schools in New Corella, Davao del Norte. This supports thee idea of Tajeddin et al. (2020) that fairness and equity in assessment are crucial for providing all students with an equal chance to demonstrate their learning and potential. Ensuring fairness and equity in assessments is essential for creating a just and inclusive educational

environment. Table 1 shows the summary on the extent of teachers' assessment literacy of junior high school students. As shown in the table, teachers' assessment literacy obtained an overall mean score 3.24, descriptively rated as moderately extensive, interpreted as sometimes observed. This implies that the range of knowledge, skills, and attitudes that enable teachers to create meaningful assessments, analyze assessment results, and apply the insights gained from assessments to improve their teaching practices is sometimes observed selected secondary public schools in New Corella, Davao del Norte. The result is congruent to Popham's (2017) findings that assessment-literate teachers understand how to design assessments that align with their instructional goals and learning objectives. This alignment ensures that the assessments accurately reflect what students are expected to learn, leading to more focused and effective teaching strategies.

Table 1. Summary on Teachers’ Assessment Literacy in New Corella, Davao Del Norte

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Fairness and Equity	3.17	Moderately Extensive
Students’ Involvement	3.24	Moderately Extensive
Feedback and Communication	3.30	Moderately Extensive
Technology in Assessment	3.18	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.24	Moderately Extensive

The table further indicates that teachers’ assessment literacy in terms of feedback and communication acquired the highest mean score of 3.30 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed, while, teachers’ assessment literacy in terms of fairness and equity acquired the lowest mean score of 3.17 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes observed. The result is in agreement to Firoozi’s et al. (2019) idea that teachers who are assessment literate can design assessments that align with their instructional goals, ensuring that assessments accurately measure what students are expected to learn. This leads to more effective teaching strategies and helps students achieve better learning outcomes.

3.2. *Assimilation Skills of Junior High School Students*—The summary on assimilation

skills of junior high school students is shown in the Table 2. As shown in the table, the overall mean of assimilation skills of junior high school students is 3.31 which is described as moderately extensive. It means that the assimilation skills of junior high school students is sometimes manifested. This shows that the ability of students to understand, process, and make sense of the information they encounter in various forms, such as texts, lectures, visuals, and multimedia is oftentimes manifested in selected secondary public schools in New Corella, Davao del Norte. The result is congruent to Buslon and Alieto’s (2019) view that extensive assimilation skills contribute to better academic performance. Students who can understand and synthesize information are more likely to excel in exams, assignments, and projects.

Table 2. Summary on Assimilation Skills of Junior High School Students among Public Secondary Schools in New Corella, Davao Del Norte

Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Visual Interpretation	3.30	Moderately Extensive
Effective Note-Taking	3.41	Moderately Extensive
Contextual Understanding	3.22	Moderately Extensive
Application to Real World Context	3.31	Moderately Extensive
Overall	3.31	Moderately Extensive

The table further indicates that assimilation skills in terms of effective note-taking acquired the highest mean score of 3.40 described as extensive and interpreted as oftentimes manifested, while, assimilation skills in terms of contextual understanding acquired the lowest mean score of 3.22 described as moderately extensive and interpreted as sometimes manifested. The results supports the proposition of Swart (2018) that students with strong assimilation skills can quickly and effectively absorb new knowledge. They can extract essential information from reading materials or lectures, reducing the time and effort required to learn new concepts. According to Uysala and Bilgeb (2018), assimilation encourages students to think critically about the material they encounter. They learn to evaluate the credibility of sources, identify biases, and distinguish between fact and opinion.

3.3. Relationship Between Teachers' Assessment Literacy and Assimilation Skills of Junior High School Students among Public Secondary Schools in New Corella, Davao Del Norte—The results on the analysis on the relationship between teachers' assessment literacy and assimilation skills of junior high school students among Public Secondary Schools in New Corella, Davao Del Norte are presented. Bivariate correlation analysis using Pearson product moment correlation was utilized to determine the relationship between the variables mentioned. Table 3 shows that teachers' assessment literacy has a significant positive relationship with the assimilation skills of junior high school students with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed)

3.4. Significant on the Influence of Teachers' Assessment Literacy on the Assimilation Skills of Junior High School Students among Public Secondary Schools in New Corella, Davao Del Norte—The significance on the in-

($r = 0.353, p < 0.05$). It means that as the extent of teachers' assessment literacy changes, assimilation skills of junior high school students also changes significantly. The table also shows that teachers' assessment literacy in terms of fairness and equity; students' involvement; feedback and communication; and technology in assessment have significant relationship with the assimilation skills of junior high school students with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = 0.250, p < 0.05$), ($r = 0.236, p < 0.05$), ($r = 0.334, p < 0.05$), and ($r = 0.201, p < 0.05$). The findings agree with the proposition of Deluca et al. (2013) that assessment-literate teachers can involve students in the assessment process by making them aware of learning goals and criteria for success. This empowers students to take ownership of their learning and set personal goals for improving their information comprehension. Similarly, Wang et al. (2022) suggested that assessment-literate teachers can create assessments that align with learning objectives and curriculum standards. This ensures that the assessments accurately measure what students are expected to learn. As a result, teachers can tailor their instruction to address specific areas where students are struggling in terms of information comprehension. According to Pastore and Andrade (2019), assessment literacy allows teachers to interpret assessment results and use the data to make informed decisions about instructional strategies. Teachers can identify patterns of misconception or misunderstanding and modify their teaching approaches to address these issues.

fluence of teachers' assessment literacy on the assimilation skills of junior high school students was analyzed using multiple linear regression analysis. The Table 4 shows that teachers' assessment literacy in terms of fairness and eq-

Table 3. Relationship Between Teachers’ Assessment Literacy and Assimilation Skills of Junior High School Students among Public Secondary Schools in New Corella, Davao Del Norte

Variables	r-value	p-value	Decision
Fairness and Equity	0.250*	0.000	Reject H0
Students’ Involvement	0.236*	0.001	Reject H0
Feedback and Communication	0.334*	0.000	Reject H0
Technology In Assessment	0.201*	0.000	Reject H0
Overall Assimilation Skills of Students	0.353*	0.000	Reject H0

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

Legend: Perfect Correlation if $r = 1.00$; Strong Correlation if $0.7 < r < 1.00$; Moderate Correlation if $0.3 \leq r < 0.7$; Weak Correlation if $0.00 < r < 0.30$; No Correlation if $r = 0.00$.

uity; students’ involvement; feedback and communication; and technology in assessment are considered, the model is significant as evident on F-value of 10.734 with $p < 0.05$. It is therefore stated that teachers’ assessment literacy predicts assimilation skills of junior high school students. Meanwhile, the computed adjusted R2 value of 0.523 indicates that teachers’ assessment literacy has contributed significantly in the variability of assimilation skills of junior high school students by 52.30% from the total variability. Therefore, the difference of 47.70% was credited to other factors not covered in this study.

In addition, table shows that there are domains of teachers’ assessment literacy that significantly influence the assimilation skills of junior high school students. This table also indicates that fairness and equity; students’ involvement; feedback and communication are significant when considered as predictors of assimilation skills of junior high school students. This means that the extent of assimilation skills of junior high school students increases by 0.190, 0.169, and 0.147 for each unit increase in teach-

ers’ assessment literacy. Thus, this leads to the rejection of null hypothesis that none of the domains of teachers’ assessment literacy that significantly influence the assimilation skills of junior high school students. Affirming that assimilation skills of junior high school students is a function of teachers’ assessment literacy, the finding is parallel to the view of Richter et al. (2021) that effective assessment literacy helps teachers provide timely and constructive feedback to students. Clear and actionable feedback helps students understand their strengths and areas for improvement, promoting deeper engagement with the material and enhancing their comprehension. Lastly, the result corroborates with Social Cognitive Theory by Bandura (1986) which posits that the quality of interactions between teachers and students, influenced by the teachers’ teaching approach and their ability to foster a caring and supportive atmosphere. The classroom setting created by teachers, characterized by their teaching methods, communication style, and classroom management practices.

Table 4. Significant on the Influence of Teachers’ Assessment Literacy on the Assimilation Skills of Junior High School Students among Public Secondary Schools in New Corella, Davao Del Norte

Indicators of Teachers’ Assessment Literacy	B	p-value	Decisions
Fairness and Equity	.190*	.006	Reject H0
Students’ Involvement	.169*	.007	Reject H0
Feedback and Communication	.147*	.046	Reject H0
Technology In Assessment	.056*	.078	Accept H0
$R^2 = 0.523$	F-value = 10.734*	p-value = 0.000	

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This part of the paper presents the conclusion and recommendation of the researcher. The discussion is supported by the literature presented in the first chapters and the conclusion is in accordance with statements of the problem presented in this study.

4.1. Findings—The primary objective of this study was to determine which domains teachers’ assessment literacy significantly influence the assimilation skills of junior high school students utilizing non-experimental quantitative design using correlation technique. The researcher selected the 210 junior high school students in New Corella, Davao Del Norte as the respondents through random sampling method. The researcher made use of modified and enhanced adapted survey questionnaires which was pilot tested in a nearby school to ensure high reliability and internal consistency of the items in the instrument. Teachers’ assessment literacy among public secondary schools in New Corella, Davao Del Norte has an overall mean of 3.24 with a descriptive rating of moderately extensive. Meanwhile, teachers’ assessment literacy in terms of fairness and equality, students’ involvement, feedback and communication, and technology in assessment obtained the mean scores of 3.17, 3.24, 3.30, and 3.18, respectively. Assimilation skills of junior high school students among public secondary schools in New Corella, Davao Del Norte has an overall mean of 3.31 with a descriptive rating of moderately extensive. Also, assimilation skills of junior high school students in terms of visual interpretation, effective note-taking, contextual understanding, and application to real world context obtained the mean scores of 3.30, 3.41, 3.22, and 3.31, respectively. Teachers’ assessment literacy has a significant positive relationship with the assimilation skills of junior high school students among public secondary schools in New Corella in Davao Del Norte with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .353, p < 0.05$). More so, teachers’ assessment literacy in terms of fairness and equality, students’ involvement, feedback and communication, and technology in assessment have significant positive relationship with the assimilation skills of junior high school students among public secondary schools in New Corella, Davao Del Norte with a p-value of .000 that is less than .05 level of significance (two-tailed) ($r = .250,$

$p < 0.05$), ($r = .236$, $p < 0.05$), ($r = .334$, $p < 0.05$), and ($r = .201$, $p < 0.05$), respectively. Teachers' assessment literacy in terms of fairness and equity; students' involvement; and feedback and communication significantly influence the assimilation skills of junior high school students among public secondary schools in New Corella in Davao Del Norte as evident on the F-value of 10.734 and $p < 0.05$. The r^2 value of 0.523 indicated that teachers' assessment literacy have contributed significantly to the variability of assimilation skills of junior high school students among public secondary schools in New Corella in Davao Del Norte by 18.60% from the total variability.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study and within the limitations and restrictions, several conclusions are generated. Teachers' assessment literacy was sometimes observed by the junior high school students among public secondary schools in New Corella, Davao Del Norte. Meanwhile, teachers' assessment literacy in terms of fairness and equality, students' involvement, feedback and communication, and technology in assessment were also described as moderately extensive. This implies that the range of knowledge, skills, and attitudes that enable teachers to create meaningful assessments, analyze assessment results, and apply the insights gained from assessments to improve their teaching practices is sometimes observed. Assimilation skills of junior high school students was oftentimes manifested among public secondary schools in New Corella, Davao Del Norte. Also, assimilation skills of junior high school students in terms of effective note-taking was described as oftentimes manifested, while, assimilation skills of junior high school students in terms of visual interpretation, contextual understanding, and application to real world context were oftentimes manifested by the junior high school students. This shows that the ability of students to understand, process, and make sense of the informa-

tion they encounter in various forms, such as texts, lectures, visuals, and multimedia is oftentimes manifested. Teachers' assessment literacy has a significant positive relationship with the assimilation skills of junior high school students among public secondary schools in New Corella in Davao Del Norte. This implies that the assessment-literate teachers can create assessments that align with learning objectives and curriculum standards. This ensures that the assessments accurately measure what students are expected to learn. As a result, teachers can tailor their instruction to address specific areas where students are struggling in terms of information comprehension. Teachers' assessment literacy in terms of fairness and equity; students' involvement; and feedback and communication significantly influence the assimilation skills of junior high school students among public secondary schools in New Corella in Davao Del Norte. This implies that effective assessment literacy helps teachers provide timely and constructive feedback to students. Clear and actionable feedback helps students understand their strengths and areas for improvement, promoting deeper engagement with the material and enhancing their comprehension.

4.3. Recommendations—The Department of Education (DepEd) should develop comprehensive policies that prioritize assessment literacy training for teachers as part of professional development programs. More so, DepEd must promote the integration of assessment literacy components into teacher education and certification programs. School heads should foster a school culture that values continuous improvement in assessment practices and encourages innovation in teaching and learning. They should also organize regular workshops and training sessions focusing on assessment literacy for teachers to improve their understanding and implementation of effective assessment practices. Teachers should engage in professional development opportunities to enhance assessment liter-

acy skills, including attending workshops, seminars, and online courses. Adding more, they should regularly reflect on assessment practices and seek feedback from colleagues and students to improve effectiveness. Students should foster a growth mindset among students, emphasizing the importance of learning from mistakes and using assessment as a tool for improvement. They should also encourage active participation in the assessment process by promoting self-assessment and reflection activities. Lastly, researchers should conduct further analysis on the factor that influence the assimilation skills of junior high school students since teachers' assessment literacy only contributed 52.30% for the total variability. Researchers should share findings and best practices through publications, conferences, and professional networks to contribute to ongoing efforts to enhance assessment practices in schools.

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